

The importance of science in the spiritual development of mankind

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ABSTRACT

The article examines the concept of science, its formation and development features, objective and subjective factors of science development, the system of sciences, the importance of science in the spiritual development of mankind, the value of science and its results, the spiritual and cultural function of scientific values.

KEYWORDS

science, the emergence of science, the development of science, science ethics, science products, intellectual activity, scientific research, scientists, scientific theories, education, scientific institutions, value, the transformation of science into value, scientific value, system of scientific values.

INTRODUCTION

The situation that is happening all over the world today has created the need to study events on a global scale. It has become the main task of modern scientists to find knowledge that can correctly explain such processes and expand the possibilities of life, able to predict the path of development. At present, in addition to the above tasks, the problems of a new approach are posed. However, research has shown that it is not limited to science alone. This provides an opportunity to look at the problem of nature, society and man in a new way, and this approach has begun to serve the solution of a number of problems facing humanity and increases the importance of the values of science in scientific knowledge. Another distinctive feature of science as a form of social consciousness is that the colorful sciences involve the study of existing phenomena and processes of being (outside of man, independent of both man and humanity). The law of universal gravitation quadratic equations, the periodic table of chemical elements, the laws of thermodynamics are objective. Their action is not determined by thoughts and moods, nor by the personality of the scientist. Science describes its conclusions in theories, laws, and formulas. In this way, he puts the individual, emotional response of the scientist to the events being studied and to the

social consequences that this or that discovery may lead to out of parentheses. Rational scientific knowledge is objective and impersonal. In other words, all the actions that science performs with its subject take on a new quality in the name of laws and regular casual relationships.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

The impact of the transformation of science into a value in the period of radical changes and renewal on the spiritual life of society is an objective-historical law inherent in the transition period. By the twentieth century, the role of science in the development of society, as well as in socio-cultural and spiritual life has increased to an unprecedented extent. As a result of the close cooperation of science with production, its ties with social life were strengthened. “The science system is generally divided into the following major groups: the natural sciences, the exact sciences, the technical sciences, and the social sciences. Many independent disciplines were separated from each of these groups. Independent disciplines have to solve large and perspective problems of scientific research in interrelated fields. This requires the development of interdisciplinary and complex research.”[1] “Scientific values” and “science values” are essentially synonymous concepts. (After all, when we say scientific knowledge, we always mean scientific knowledge). The great German philosopher I. Kant actively supported the tradition of distinguishing between the concepts of knowledge, thought and belief, and was the first to show the need to differentiate between the concepts of knowledge and value. The distinction between knowledge and value does not preclude, but requires the study of value on a scientific basis and the understanding of knowledge, science as a value. Scientific values, as an important component of our spiritual values and a fundamental value, are distinguished by a number of features, the laws of development. Understanding science as a value requires, first of all, a deep understanding of scientific knowledge and the great creative power of science in society and individual life, the role of salvation, the development of scientific knowledge, the freedom of speech, press and conscience, the establishment of democratic values. reaches Before defining the place and role of scientific values in the system of spiritual values, it is expedient to think about its essence, composition and functions. At the same time, first of all, it should be noted that scientific values are relative. Science is understood as a value not for all members of society, but only by

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the highest elite of society (intellectuals, entrepreneurs, officials). At the same time, for intellectuals who have devoted their entire conscious life to science, scientific values are understood as the highest value, the meaning of life, the means of expressing identity. It should also be emphasized that scientific values are universal values. Everyone, regardless of their social origin, race, nationality, gender, has the right to enjoy and develop scientific values in order to realize their spiritual and intellectual values and talents. The constitutions of all democracies emphasize that the right of every citizen to education is guaranteed by the state. Understanding science as a value is a natural human right, not a privilege granted to any class, class or class in society. However, to exercise this natural right, people are required to have intellectual capacity, strong memory, critical thinking skills, and a love of truth. People begin to look at science with a special interest and love from an early age in order to realize their God-given innate intellectual abilities. Those who understand science as a value and dedicate themselves to it do not see science as a means to live an easy, prosperous and fulfilling life. Perhaps, on the contrary, they are subjected to their own toil and boundless toil, but they find pleasure and enjoyment in the toil of knowledge, in every innovation they have achieved. Scientific values are a set of ideas, works, educational and scientific institutions, a team of scientists, scientists, which allow to realize the intellectual and spiritual abilities and talents of people, to study the scientific heritage of our ancestors, to create innovations and discoveries through the study of reality. Both the subject and the object of scientific values are hard-working scientists. The attitude of the whole society towards science is clearly seen in the attitude towards scientists. Caring for a scientist, sponsoring science, supporting it in every way is the main task of a democratic and progressive state. In this regard, President Sh. Mirziyoyev's views are noteworthy: "Supporting the activities and research of leading scientists, talented young scientists, increasing the prestige and prestige of scientists in society will remain one of the priorities of our state" [1]. The peace and enjoyment that science gives is superior to any other pleasure. Admittedly, the flavor that emerges here is a real and simple blessing. It is not about deception. Because of science, man ascends to the heavenly heights, and his body is incapable of doing so. The values of science are not only the manifestation of talent, but also an effective influence on the discovery, mastery of the laws of society, nature and the development of thinking, the acquisition of skills of epistemological, intellectual approach to existence, increasing the scientific potential of society. In this sense, scientific values are essentially the realization of people's

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ability to think theoretically, the need to study the laws of evolution, the deep study of scientific heritage, ideas and fundamental works that encourage innovation and discovery, as well as educational and scientific institutions, researchers. a team of scientists, a set of scientists.

CONCLUSION

In short, scientific values take a leading position in the system of spiritual values of an industrialized society, developing as a basic value. On the basis of scientific value, all elements of spiritual values (moral, political, legal, ideological, artistic, philosophical values, etc.) are intellectualized. Especially in the context of the scientific and technological revolution, the ethics of science, the responsibility of the scientist is the fundamental basis of scientific values. In the current conditions of building civil society in our country, the high civic position of scientists, their devotion to the development of science, devotion to the motherland and our people are of great importance

REFERENCES

1. Uzbek national encyclopedia. 9 tom. - pp. 182-183
2. Mirziyoev Sh.M. (2017) Resolutely continuing our path of national development. We will rise to a new level. Tashkent: “Uzbekistan”. –p. 176.
3. Abramyan L.A. (1979) Kant and the problem of knowledge. Yerevan: published by An Arm.SSR, - p.36.
4. Mirzarakhimov, B. Kh. (2019). Tourism culture as a strategy for the development of bibliology. In promising areas of science and technology development -pp. 57-58.

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